

Dynamic regression of n-of-1 observational data

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In this document, I present a script in R that can be used as a template for statistical analysis in the context of observational studies of a single subject (N-of-1 studies). This script translates into R language a SPSS pipeline proposed by Suzanne McDonald and colleagues in a 2020 paper. I apply the script to the same dataset provided in the paper.

1 Introduction

Single-case studies, commonly referred to as N-of-1 studies, are common in the context of rare diseases. But while the theoretic and operative framework for genetic analyses of single subjects suspected of a Mendelian disorder is already relatively well established (1), a lack of consensus has been reported on the statistical methodologies to employ when assessing the effect of predictors in observational studies carried out on a single patient, with repeated measures over time (2-4).

These same methodologies are likely to benefit the population of individuals affected by common diseases as well, where a personalized approach has been advocated for (5). Moreover, the use of wearables, devices that upload to servers all sorts of daily metrics (heart rate variability, hemodynamic measures, number of steps, caloric and macronutrient intake, simplified EEG readings, and so forth) making them available for download on PCs as CSV or TSV files, will likely boost the diffusion of N-of-1 studies in the context of both rare diseases and personalized medicine. An emerging area of application is linked to the rise of decentralized science, with patients directly involved in the study of their maladies, especially in the case of neglected diseases (6).

Inappropriate methodologies have often been employed in N-of-1 studies, like qualitative approaches or methods based on the hypothesis of independence of the observations, like correlation coefficients, T-testing, and regression (7). Since we are dealing with time series, standard regression is generally not suited because in the presence of positive autocorrelation for the independent variable it may overestimate the effect of a predictor (Type I error), while negative autoregression leads to underestimation (Type II error) (8). Different statistical methods are available for rigorous handling of data from N-of-1 studies, and dynamic regression represents probably the simplest approach among them (3, 4, 9).

2 McDonald's dataset

This paragraph follows all the steps of the dynamic regression illustrated by McDonald and colleagues using a real observational N-of-1 dataset (4). The aim is to show how to perform with the statistical language R all the analyses executed employing SPSS by the authors. The script can serve as a backbone for the dynamic regression of different datasets.

The subject of this experiment is a 39-year-old man with chronic myalgia and arthralgia. At 7:30 am a pain score is collected (a number from 0 to 1) and an accelerometer worn by the subject starts recording physical activity for 24 hours. The experiment was repeated for 89 consecutive days.

Data can be downloaded from:

https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/instance/8114402/bin/RHPB_A_1711096_SM0155.zip

To read the SAV file, we need package haven. We read the table and look at its first rows:

```
library(haven)
```

```
#
mydata<-as.data.frame(read_sav("Illustrative example data.sav")) # read data
head(mydata) # inspect data
```

We see that for each day of the experiment, three measures are available. PA_24h is the outcome variable, the measure of the accelerometer on 24 hours; pain is the value assigned at 7:30 am, at the beginning of the 24 hours of kinematic recording; week of the day is 1 during weekend, zero otherwise.

	studyday	week_day	pain	PA_24h
1	1	0	0.62	100
2	2	0	0.91	78
3	3	0	0.80	75
4	4	0	0.84	43
5	5	0	0.31	125
6	6	1	0.74	40

We then visually inspect the data, by plotting pain and PA_24h (Figure 1):

```
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
plot(mydata$studyday,mydata$pain,type="l",col=1,lwd=2,xlab="day",ylab="pain")
plot(mydata$studyday,mydata$PA_24h,type="l",col=1,lwd=2,xlab="day",ylab="PA")
```


Figure 1. Plots for the time series of pain (left) and of PA_24h (right). The day of the experiment is on the x-axis.

No missing data are detected in this data frame, otherwise, imputation would have been necessary, using function `approx` for instance.

Then we check for the presence of trends in the mean value of the outcome variable or its standard deviation (SD). If a trend for the mean is present, for instance, a linear trend, time should be included as a covariate. The constraint over SD comes from the general theory of linear regression (8). To study the evolution over time for mean and SD, we must select a moving time window and compute the moments of the dependent variable within the window, as it moves along the time axis. First, we build a data frame with SD and mean for each window:

```
window<-5 # temporal width of time window
n.days<-nrow(mydata) # total number of days available
n.window<-round(n.days/window) # number of windows
stat.df<-data.frame(window=seq(1:n.window),mean=rep(NA,n.window),sd=rep(NA,n.window))
d<-1
for (i in 1:(n.window)) {
  stat.df$mean[i]<-mean(mydata$PA_24h[d:(d+window-1)])
  stat.df$sd[i]<-sd(mydata$PA_24h[d:(d+window-1)])
}
```

```
d<-d+window
}
```

Then we regress mean and SD against the window ordinal number (time):

```
model.mean<-lm(mean~window,data=stat.df)
summary(model.mean)
model.sd<-lm(sd~window,data=stat.df)
summary(model.sd)
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
plot(stat.df$window,stat.df$mean,pch=19,col="blue",xlab="window",ylab="mean")
abline(model.mean,col="red",lwd=2)
plot(stat.df$window,stat.df$sd,pch=19,col="blue",xlab="window",ylab="sd")
abline(model.sd,col="red",lwd=2)
```

The two linear regressions (Figure 2) are not significant.

Figure 2. Linear regression and data for mean (left) and SD (right) against time (ordinal number of moving time window). None of the regressions is significant.

Figure 3. Decomposition of the time series PA_24h with function stl.

The search for trends or periodicity in the outcome variable can also be done qualitatively by decomposition of the time series with an additive model like the one implemented by function stl:

```
PA_24h.ts<-ts(mydata$PA_24h,frequency=7) # we need to introduce a window for stl
```

```
PA_24h.dec<-stl(PA_24h.ts,s.window=5)
plot(PA_24h.dec)
```

We see that there isn't a clear pattern across the experiment, neither for trend nor for periodicity.

Next, we study the autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation functions, which should provide information on the endogenous dynamic variables to build and introduce among the covariates (if any). What I meant will be clear in a moment. In R autocorrelation computation is straightforward:

```
PA_24h.ts<-ts(mydata$PA_24h,frequency=1) # transform outcome in a ts object
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
acf(PA_24h.ts,lwd=2) # autocorrelation
pacf(PA_24h.ts,lwd=2) # autocorrelation corrected for previous lags (partial acf)
```


Figure 4. Autocorrelation function (left) and partial autocorrelation function (right) for the time series PA_24h.

We see a positive autocorrelation with the outcome of the previous two days. This suggests introducing as covariates the values of PA_24h with a lag of one and two days. But should we also add more lagged values? We see from the partial autocorrelation (autocorrelation corrected for previous lagged values) that these two lagged values are sufficient to account for autocorrelation.

We can now build the two endogenous covariates:

```
Lag1<-c()
Lag1[1]<-NA
for (i in 2:n.days) {
  Lag1[i]<-mydata$PA_24h[i-1]
}
#
Lag2<-c()
Lag2[1]<-NA
Lag2[2]<-NA
for (i in 3:n.days) {
  Lag2[i]<-mydata$PA_24h[i-2]
}
#
mydata$Lag1<-Lag1
mydata$Lag2<-Lag2
```

This algorithm has been successful if the regression between the outcome and the lagged variables generates residuals with no sign of autocorrelation. To check whether this condition is satisfied we calculate the regression and study the residuals:

```
model<-lm(PA_24h~Lag1+Lag2,data=mydata)
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
residuals.ts<-ts(model$residuals,frequency=1) # transform residuals in a ts object
acf(residuals.ts,lwd=2) # autocorrelation
pacf(residuals.ts,lwd=2) # autocorrelation corrected for previous lags (partial acf)
```

We see from Figure 5 that we have been successful.

Figure 5. Autocorrelation function (left) and partial autocorrelation function (right) for the time series of the residuals of the linear regression $PA_{24h} \sim Lag1 + Lag2$.

The last step is to perform the dynamic regression and examine the signs and significance of the regression coefficients:

```
model<-lm(PA_24h~Lag1+Lag2+pain,data=mydata)
summary(model)
```

The conclusion is that we detected a significant negative correlation between the pain score at 7:30 am and the physical activity in the following 24 hours. Moreover, as already pointed out, physical activity regresses positively with lagged measures over one and two days.

```
Call:
lm(formula = PA_24h ~ Lag1 + Lag2 + pain, data = mydata)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-67.676 -33.215   0.586  23.826 109.799

Coefficients:
(Intercept)  87.5383  20.2157  4.330 4.23e-05 ***
Lag1          0.1797   0.1047  1.717  0.0899 .
Lag2          0.2491   0.1050  2.372  0.0201 *
pain        -59.8562  24.7844 -2.415  0.0180 *
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 37.97 on 81 degrees of freedom
```

```
(2 osservazioni eliminate a causa di valori mancanti)
Multiple R-squared: 0.1621, Adjusted R-squared: 0.131
F-statistic: 5.222 on 3 and 81 DF, p-value: 0.002397
```

3 The script for the first example

```
# file name: NofOne
#
# Rome 6th December 2024
#
path<-getwd() # current directory
#
#-----
# Packages and files
#-----
#
library(haven)
#
#-----
# Data
#-----
#
mydata<-as.data.frame(read_sav("Illustrative example data.sav")) # read data
head(mydata) # inspect data
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
plot(mydata$studyday,mydata$pain,type="l",col=1,lwd=2,xlab="day",ylab="pain")
plot(mydata$studyday,mydata$PA_24h,type="l",col=1,lwd=2,xlab="day",ylab="PA")
#
#-----
# Is the outcome stationary?
#-----
#
window<-5 # temporal width of time window
n.days<-nrow(mydata) # total number of days available
n.window<-round(n.days/window) # number of windows
stat.df<-data.frame(window=seq(1:n.window),mean=rep(NA,n.window),sd=rep(NA,n.window))
d<-1
for (i in 1:(n.window)) {
  stat.df$mean[i]<-mean(mydata$PA_24h[d:(d+window-1)])
  stat.df$sd[i]<-sd(mydata$PA_24h[d:(d+window-1)])
  d<-d+window
}
model.mean<-lm(mean~window,data=stat.df)
summary(model.mean)
model.sd<-lm(sd~window,data=stat.df)
summary(model.sd)
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
plot(stat.df$window,stat.df$mean,pch=19,col="blue",xlab="window",ylab="mean")
abline(model.mean,col="red",lwd=2)
plot(stat.df$window,stat.df$sd,pch=19,col="blue",xlab="window",ylab="sd")
abline(model.sd,col="red",lwd=2)
#
#-----
# Decomposition
#-----
#
PA_24h.ts<-ts(mydata$PA_24h,frequency=7) # we need to introduce a window for stl
PA_24h.dec<-stl(PA_24h.ts,s.window=5)
```

```

plot(PA_24h.dec)
#
#-----
# Autocorrelation and decomposition
#-----
#
PA_24h.ts<-ts(mydata$PA_24h,frequency=1) # transform outcome in a ts object
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
acf(PA_24h.ts,lwd=2) # autocorrelation
pacf(PA_24h.ts,lwd=2) # autocorrelation corrected for previous lags (partial acf)
#
#-----
# Create lagged variables and add to data frame
#-----
#
Lag1<-c()
Lag1[1]<-NA
for (i in 2:n.days) {
  Lag1[i]<-mydata$PA_24h[i-1]
}
#
Lag2<-c()
Lag2[1]<-NA
Lag2[2]<-NA
for (i in 3:n.days) {
  Lag2[i]<-mydata$PA_24h[i-2]
}
#
mydata$Lag1<-Lag1
mydata$Lag2<-Lag2
#
#-----
# Autocorrelation of residuals
#-----
#
model<-lm(PA_24h~Lag1+Lag2,data=mydata)
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
residuals.ts<-ts(model$residuals,frequency=1) # transform residuals in a ts object
acf(residuals.ts,lwd=2) # autocorrelation
pacf(residuals.ts,lwd=2) # autocorrelation corrected for previous lags (partial acf)
#
#-----
# Dynamic regression
#-----
#
model<-lm(PA_24h~Lag1+Lag2+pain,data=mydata)
summary(model)

```

References

1. Gonzaga-Jauregui C, Lupski JR. Genomics of rare diseases. Waltham: Elsevier; 2021. pages cm p.
2. Duan N, Kravitz RL, Schmid CH. Single-patient (n-of-1) trials: a pragmatic clinical decision methodology for patient-centered comparative effectiveness research. J Clin Epidemiol. 2013;66(8 Suppl):S21-8.

3. Vieira R, McDonald S, Araújo-Soares V, Sniehotta F, Henderson R. Dynamic modelling of n-of-1 data: Powerful and flexible data analytics applied to individualised studies. *Health Psychology Review*. 2017;11:1-32.
4. McDonald S, Vieira R, Johnston DW. Analysing N-of-1 observational data in health psychology and behavioural medicine: a 10-step SPSS tutorial for beginners. *Health Psychol Behav Med*. 2020;8(1):32-54.
5. Schork NJ. Personalized medicine: Time for one-person trials. *Nature*. 2015;520(7549):609-11.
6. Maccallini P. 2024. Available from: <https://paolomaccallini.wordpress.com/2024/10/10/my-longitudinal-study-machine-learning-and-more/>.
7. McDonald S, Quinn F, Vieira R, O'Brien N, White M, Johnston DW, et al. The state of the art and future opportunities for using longitudinal n-of-1 methods in health behaviour research: a systematic literature overview. *Health Psychol Rev*. 2017;11(4):307-23.
8. Montgomery DC, Peck EA, Vining GG. *Introduction to Linear Regression Analysis*: Wiley; 2013.
9. Flandoli F. *Dispense di Statistica II*: University of Pisa; 2013.